

Post-Survey

Student Name: _____ Student ID: _____

Instructions: This questionnaire gives you the opportunity to provide information on your experience working on the group project and share your experiences communicating with your team mates to complete the project. *Please fill out the questions below in the context of completing the group project in this course.*

1. What is your level of satisfaction with the team in this last project?
2. Did you experience gender bias while working on the project?
 - a. No
 - b. Don't know
 - c. Yes, positive and negative
 - d. Yes, mostly positive
 - e. Yes, mostly negative
3. Did gender imbalance affect you at meetings or discussions with your team mates?
 - a. Don't know
 - b. Not at all
 - c. Not really
 - d. To some extent
 - e. Yes
4. Do you believe the "boy's club" mentality was present while working on the group project?
 - a. Don't know
 - b. Not at all
 - c. Not really
 - d. To some extent
 - e. Yes
5. I felt included while working on group activities with my team mates.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)

6. I was mindful in my communication approach while working on the group project.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)

7. During the group project, my questions and input was ignored by my teammates.
 - a. Never (1)
 - b. Rarely (2)
 - c. Sometimes (3)
 - d. Very Often (4)
 - e. Always (5)

8. I received verbal abuse while working on the group project.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)

9. The behavior of my team mates sometimes made me feel uncomfortable.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)